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SERVICES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NETWORK OF THE LANDSCAPING SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article describes the importance of landscaping services, the regulation of improving the activities of the sector on the basis of various regulations. At the same time, proposals and recommendations have been developed around the world to prevent the harmful effects of waste on human life and health, the environment, reduce waste generation and ensure their rational use in economic activities.

Keywords: Landscaping, Landscaping Services, Landscaping Area, Landscaping Department, Tasks, Solid Waste, Waste Disposal Service.

I. Introduction.

It is no exaggeration to say that landscaping services are one of the areas that have already established themselves as one of the separate areas with the types of services available today. Landscaping services are one of the areas that are becoming a special focus of the population, along with the coverage of all developed and developing countries.

The explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language states that “landscaping is the beautification, beautification is the addition of beauty. At the same time, prosperity, beauty, construction of landscaping, landscaping and construction works”.

Landscaping areas can be called green areas, including areas adjacent to very large, large and large cities, agricultural lands, landscape-recreation zones, small settlements and other facilities. We believe that it would be expedient to calculate the labor resources and determine the development indicators of urban subsystems, taking into account the daily labor and cultural ties with the settlements around the city center, to analyze the correct and systematic implementation of landscaping.

II. Literature review

The following scholars have considered services in the development of the network of the landscaping system in their research: Khmelchenko E.G. [5], Konyshva L.A. [6], Muxamedjanov A. [7].

Noting that Uzbekistan pays great attention to landscaping services, its activities are improved and regulated on the basis of various regulations, it is worth noting that no research has been conducted on the development of these services.

In order to effectively develop landscaping services and pay special attention to this type of service, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to improve the organization of landscaping of settlements" dated January 10, 2013 No 4 and President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev Resolution No. PQ-4351 "On additional measures to increase the efficiency of work in the field of improvement of settlements". In accordance with this decision, the issue of modernizing the existing cities, district centers, urban settlements and rural settlements in the country was raised.

In order to solve this problem, it is necessary to take consistent measures to improve landscaping through the establishment of landscaping departments on the basis of existing organizations (divisions) on landscaping in districts and cities of the country. new tasks for development and updating have been identified.

III. Research methodology

In the implementation of the study, conclusions and recommendations were formed as a result of the analysis of indicators of effective development of landscaping services through economic methods. In addition, the methods of analysis and synthesis were effectively used in the study of landscaping by zoning in the conduct of scientific research.

IV. Analysis and results

Analyzing the daily activities of each city is about facing a number of problems in that city that need to be addressed. The most noteworthy aspect is that the development of landscaping services is one of the main indicators of the economic and social stability of this country. However, one of the most important problems in the development of the network of landscaping systems is the lack of attention today to the improvement of this network. Therefore, it should be noted that all cities and district centers of the country are significantly different from each other.

For all developed countries of the world, ecological cleanliness in cities, especially in the capitals of the country, will be the focus of special attention of all levels of government, political parties, social movements, the media and the population.

Urban beautification has always been the most urgent task. The word landscaping can be understood in two different senses: in the narrow sense and in the broad sense.

First, in the narrow sense - a house, a yard and an area that belongs only to one person or family members.

Second, in a broad sense - planning, communal construction, housing and land issues, sidewalks, urban green spaces, street maintenance, street transport, urban

communications, urban lighting, heating, urban ecology, pedestrian traffic congestion including.

Urban development is a "mirror" that reflects the socio-economic status and level of the city, so it is no coincidence that in developed countries, information about the country's prosperity, its ecological situation is open to the public and plays a leading role in political and social life.

Year by year population growth, urban growth, industrial development, all this leads to the problem of urban beautification, the problem of keeping the environment clean, the creation of small and invisible barriers to creating adequate conditions for human life and activity. If we look at the last decades, we can see that the negative impact of people on the environment and especially on urban development has increased significantly.

Today, large-scale projects are being implemented around the world to prevent the harmful effects of waste on human life and health, the environment, reduce waste generation and ensure their rational use in economic activities. This is because more than 2 billion tons of solid household waste is generated worldwide each year, and at least 33 percent of it is recycled in environmentally safe ways. The average daily per capita household waste is 0.74 kg, with its lower and upper limits fluctuating between 0.1 and 4.5 kg across regions. In East Asia and the Pacific, about 23 percent of the world's waste is generated, while in the Middle East and North Africa it is the lowest, at 6 percent.

In many countries, several levels of government are involved in solid waste recycling, with local authorities playing a key role. Local authorities play an important role in waste collection, transportation and recycling. They may also have the authority to set the amount of payment for waste removal, waste disposal, and the issuance of licenses and permits for recycling is often done by the state or its territorial authorities.

If we look at the worldwide definitions of payments for this type of service, we think that the main focus should be on:

In U.S. cities, waste collection is usually done at a single rate. The average monthly cost of this service ranges from \$ 9 to \$ 70. Residents of Chicago-based apartment buildings pay an average of \$ 9.5 per home per month for the waste transportation service provided by the Department of Street and Sanitation. This amount, along with water and sewerage services, is included in the general utility bill.

In Toronto, Canada, and Sydney, Australia, there is a tariff program based on the size of the waste container. The fee is \$ 270-516, which includes garbage

collection, collection and recycling of street waste, organic, oversized and metal objects, as well as old electronics.

In Amsterdam, the payment for waste is made depending on the number of citizens living in the family, while a one-person apartment costs 326 euros per year, while a family of several can spend up to 435 euros.

In Seoul, citizens pay a general fee for an apartment, which includes services such as electricity, water, cleaning the area, servicing elevators, and garbage collection. The fee for waste is included in the "additional services" and is set at no more than 10% of the total payment. Another distinctive feature of the South Korean waste recycling system is the separate collection of food waste. Each waste collection point has a separate container for food waste disposal, but it can only be opened by residents of residential buildings attached to this waste collection point through a special card.

The weight of food waste included in the box is automatically measured in the box and recorded in the citizen's account, at the end of the month all accounts are summed, the cost of disposing of the waste is deducted and added to the total payment for the apartment.

In general, these countries have legislation governing the classification, collection, transportation and recycling of domestic, industrial and hazardous waste.

The scope of sanitary cleaning services is growing in Uzbekistan, including 13 state unitary enterprises "Clean Zone" consisting of 174 district (city) branches in the regions, which are actively involved in business through transparent mechanisms for connecting territories on the basis of electronic tenders.

The low level of payment discipline has a negative impact on the financial performance of organizations providing solid waste collection and disposal services (hereinafter - service organizations), limits the opportunities to invest in the renewal of fixed assets and improve the quality of services, as well as attracts businesses in this area.

One of the main tasks today is to further develop the system of household waste, strengthen payment discipline in the field of collection and disposal of solid waste, increase the level of access to quality sanitation services.

The generation of waste depends on many factors, the most important of which are the income of the population, consumer behavior, the emergence of new packaged products on the market and demographic indicators. According to estimates, the forecast of annual production of solid waste in the country is estimated at 14-14.5 million tons, and given the average population growth rate of 1.5%, this figure could reach 16-16.7 million tons by 2028.

Taking into account the above information, today in the development of the field of landscaping in our country it is important to take into account regional factors in choosing the organizational form of management of the service system. We found it necessary to include the following in the regional factors.

Figure 1. Factors of development of regional landscaping of cities.

The use of this process-oriented approach is important in the development of regional landscaping services. As a result, there are rules for the implementation of the strategy for the development of services in the field of landscaping, and their implementation is relevant for the well-being of citizens.

V. Conclusion/recommendations

From the above data, we can conclude that in recent years the formation of a modern image of urban centers, neighborhoods, adaptation of road transport and engineering-communication infrastructure to modern standards and requirements, their reconstruction and modernization will increase the number and weight of tourists.

The system of landscaping services will be radically improved by strengthening the material and technical base of landscaping services in regional and district centers and mahallas, equipping them with modern special vehicles and mechanization, providing landscaping staff with special work clothes and providing them with appropriate incentives.

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